

Steroid- and immunosuppressive-resistant nephrotic syndrome in focal and segmental glomerulosclerosis and hyalinosis (FSGSH) with progressive chronic kidney disease: diagnostic and therapeutic challenges

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Received 16 December 2025 ♦ Accepted 4 January 2026 ♦ Published 20 January 2026

Citation: Nikolov D, Nikolov G, Kitov S, Kitova M-F, Mihaylova AA, Kitova L (2026) Steroid- and immunosuppressive-resistant nephrotic syndrome in focal and segmental glomerulosclerosis and hyalinosis (FSGSH) with progressive chronic kidney disease: diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e182594>

Abstract

This report presents a complex case of an 18-year-old patient with multiresistant nephrotic syndrome secondary to focal and segmental glomerulosclerosis and hyalinosis (FSGSH), characterized by massive proteinuria (47 to 11 g/24 h), severe hypoproteinemia (albumin 6–17 g/L), immunologic abnormalities (C3, IgM, and C1q deposits), dysregulation of the alternative complement pathway, and a lack of response to standard, combined, and biological therapies. The clinical course included a progressive decline in eGFR, development of anemia, hypercoagulability, infectious complications, and the need for ultrafiltration and hemodialysis. This case reflects the therapeutic limitations in FSGSH and highlights the need for personalized, pathophysiology-based treatment strategies.

Keywords

biologic therapy, calcineurin inhibitors, corticosteroids, focal and segmental glomerulosclerosis and hyalinosis (FSGSH), immunosuppressants, nephrotic syndrome, plasma exchange, ravulizumab, rituximab

Introduction

FSGSH is a heterogeneous glomerular disease characterized by podocyte injury, sclerosis of glomerular capillary loops, and massive nephrotic proteinuria. It may be primary (idiopathic) or secondary. Steroid-resistant forms

are associated with an extremely poor prognosis and rapid progression to end-stage kidney disease. This case reflects the therapeutic limitations in FSGSH and highlights the need for personalized, pathophysiology-based treatment strategies [1–4]. Evidence supporting the involvement of complement activation in disease pathogenesis is increas-

ing, and novel biologic therapies targeting C5 or C5aR are being investigated.

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) and nephrotic syndrome remain major clinical challenges due to their multifactorial pathogenesis and limited therapeutic options. Cases of therapy-resistant nephrotic syndrome associated with FSGSH often require a combined and prolonged therapeutic approach.

This report presents a case of a young patient with severe nephrotic syndrome and CKD managed through a multidisciplinary strategy (Barbour and Cattran 2019; Ronco and Fervenza 2021).

Case description

Patient: P.I., 18-year-old male.

Follow-up period: 2023–2025.

Diagnoses:

- Focal and segmental glomerulosclerosis and hyalinosis (FSGSH);
- Nephrotic syndrome, steroid- and immunosuppressant-resistant;
- Chronic kidney disease, stage 4;
- Anasarca;
- Symptomatic renal anemia;
- Erysipelas as a complication during therapy.

Clinical presentation

The patient presented with marked generalized edema (anasarca), periorbital and peripheral swelling, rapid weight gain (+9 kg in 2 weeks), fatigue, reduced physical activity, hypertension up to 155/95 mmHg, decreased urine output, and orthostatic weakness.

Diagnostic evaluation

Kidney biopsy Light microscopy

Among 28 glomeruli:

- Nine with segmental sclerosis;
- Three with global sclerosis;
- Two presenting a collapsing variant (poor prognosis).

Additional findings included podocyte hypertrophy with microvillus transformation, mosaic capillary loop injury, and collagenization of Bowman's capsule.

Immunofluorescence

- C3 +++;
- IgM ++;
- C1q +.

Interpretation: activation of the alternative complement pathway triggered by podocyte injury.

Electron microscopy

Diffuse foot process effacement, podocyte thinning with focal necrosis, and subendothelial electron-dense deposits lacking a pattern typical of genetic forms were observed. No organized immune deposits were identified.

Genetic analysis

A 773-gene nephropathy panel revealed:

- No pathogenic variants in NPHS1, NPHS2, INF2, ACTN4, WT1, or COL4A;
- Variants of uncertain significance in CFH and CFI (no proven functional impact).

Genetic etiology not confirmed.

Treatment

1. Corticosteroids

- Methylprednisolone pulses (0.5 g/day × 3);
- Prednisolone up to 60 mg/day.

Minimal effect was observed; steroid resistance was confirmed.

2. Immunosuppressants

Cyclosporine: poor proteinuria control; nephrotoxicity.

Mycophenolate mofetil: partial stabilization, no remission.

Table 1. Laboratory trends during follow-up.

Year/Period	Creatinine (μmol/L)	eGFR (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	Proteinuria (g/24h)	Albumin (g/L)	Hemoglobin (g/L)	Notes
2023 initial abnormalities	~110	~70	12	24	120	Onset of proteinuria and hypoalbuminemia
2023 rapid escalation	~160	45	47	10–12	~100	Massive proteinuria, anasarca, rapid loss of renal function
2024 progressive deterioration	220–240	~25	20–30	6–10	90–95	Stable but severely impaired renal function; persistent nephrotic proteinuria
2025 current status	≥250	<20	11	6–17	80–90	–

3. Biologic therapy

Rituximab: 2 × 500 mg; no sustained benefit.

Ravulizumab: limited efficacy, likely due to irreversible podocyte injury and late initiation.

4. Plasma exchange

Provided transient improvement in edema, with no modification of the long-term renal trajectory.

5. Hemodialysis and ultrafiltration

Initiated for refractory hypervolemia, azotemia, hyperkalemia, and anemia.

6. Supportive care

- High-dose diuretics;
- Albumin infusions;
- Anticoagulation with enoxaparin;
- Targeted antibiotic therapy for erysipelas;
- Electrolyte and fluid optimization.

7. Clinical course

Despite optimal therapy, proteinuria remained massive, albumin levels were critically low, and renal function continued to decline. The patient required repeated hospitalizations for edema, hypertension, and infections and ultimately regular ultrafiltration and hemodialysis (Barbour and Cattran 2019; Ronco and Fervenza 2021).

Discussion

This case emphasizes several critical clinical points.

1. Typical therapeutic resistance in FSGSH

The patient demonstrated non-responsiveness to:

- Corticosteroids;
- Calcineurin inhibitors;
- Mycophenolate mofetil;
- Rituximab;
- Ravulizumab.

This profile is consistent with immunologically active but structurally advanced disease. Complement inhibition was justified but was likely introduced too late.

2. Complement activation

Immunofluorescence findings and genetic VUS variants indicate activation and dysregulation of the alternative complement pathway.

3. Complications of severe hypoalbuminemia

These included increased infection risk, impaired pharmacokinetics of medications (including anticoagulants), refractory edema, and irreversible renal deterioration.

4. Importance of a multidisciplinary strategy

Management required expertise from nephrology, clinical immunology, clinical pharmacology, cardiology, and infectious disease.

Conclusion

This case illustrates the complexity and limitations of available therapies for resistant nephrotic syndrome associated with FSGSH. Persistent proteinuria, complement activation, and early structural glomerular injury underscore the need for:

- Earlier initiation of targeted biologics;
- Individualized treatment based on immunologic and genetic profiles;
- Development of novel podocyte- and complement-directed therapies;
- Integrated pharmaceutical care during intensive immunosuppression (Sethi and Fervenza 2012; Fervenza and Appel 2017; Barbour and Cattran 2019; Ronco and Fervenza 2021).

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Clinic of Nephrology, St. George University Hospital, Plovdiv, Bulgaria. Patient anonymity has been preserved throughout.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

D.N.: conceptualization of the study, patient management, manuscript drafting, and critical revisions; G.N.: literature review, data collection, and interpretation of clinical findings; M.F.K.: preparation of tables and discussion section; S.K.: diagnostic data analysis, evaluation, and clinical correlation; A.M.: pharmacological review and contribution to manuscript editing; L.K.: supervision, final approval of the manuscript, and overall coordination of the study. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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